

Особливості формування кадрової безпеки в системі управління аграрних підприємств в умовах сучасних ризиків

Актуальність теми дослідження. Дослідження питання особливостей формування кадрової безпеки в системі управління аграрних підприємств в умовах сучасних ризиків обумовлюється відсутністю єдиного підходу до реалізації алгоритму даного процесу.

Постановка проблеми. У даний час важливе місце у генеруванні інноваційного розвитку аграрних підприємств в національній економіці займає кадрова безпека. Ефективна кадрова безпека сприяє формуванню конкурентного середовища в аграрному секторі. Кадрова безпека має значно підсилювати свій позитивний вплив на систему управління підприємством, за рахунок чого змінює та задається подальший тренд розвитку національного агросектору за рахунок міцної кадрової політики. Дане питання в контексті сучасних ризиків обумовлює актуальність теми дослідження.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – дослідити особливості формування кадрової безпеки в системі управління аграрних підприємств в умовах сучасних ризиків.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано наступні методи: монографічний, аналізу і синтезу, систематизації.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Визначено щільний діалектичний взаємозв'язок між ринком праці, кадровою безпекою та інноваційним розвитком підприємства у агросфері. Ринок праці є продуцентом інноваційного підприємництва та міцної кадрової безпеки. За рахунок наявності на ринку праці людських ресурсів, які задіяні у виробництві та розповсюдженні інноваційних товарів і послуг в агросекторі. Основною гіпотезою у сформованому контексті є те, що без урахування тенденцій, що відбуваються на сучасному ринку праці практично неможливо сформулювати засоби державної підтримки інноваційного розвитку агросектору та шляхів забезпечення кадрової безпеки.

Галузь застосування результатів. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані в практичній діяльності аграрних підприємств для зменшення негативного впливу ризиків на систему кадрової безпеки.

Висновки за статтю. Визначено основні напрямки формування кадрової безпеки аграрних підприємств. Акцентовано увагу, що інноваційне підприємництво у агросекторі підсилює свій позитивний вплив на ринок праці, яке змінює та задає подальший тренд розвитку національного ринку праці за рахунок стійкої кадрової безпеки. У такому взаємозв'язку відбувається синергетичний ефект дії підприємництва в агросекторі, кадрової безпеки та ринку праці, що обумовлює та визначає поточний та перспективний вектор розвитку національної інноваційної системи.

Ключові слова: кадрова безпека, система управління, аграрні підприємства, ризик, ринок праці.

ZOSY-KIOR M. V., HNATENKO I. A.,
ILIN V. Yu., PROKOPENKO O. V.

Peculiarities of the formation of personnel security in the management system of agrarian enterprises in the conditions of modern risks

Relevance of the research topic. The study of the peculiarities of the formation of personnel security in the management system of agricultural enterprises in the conditions of modern risks is conditioned by the lack of a unified approach to the implementation of the algorithm of this process.

Formulation of the problem. Currently, an important place in the generation of innovative development of agricultural enterprises in the national economy is occupied by personnel security.

Effective personnel security contributes to the formation of a competitive environment in the agricultural sector. Personnel security should significantly strengthen its positive influence on the enterprise management system, due to which changes and sets the further trend of the development of the national agricultural sector due to a strong personnel policy. This issue in the context of modern risks determines the relevance of the research topic.

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – to investigate the peculiarities of the formation of personnel security in the management system of agrarian enterprises in the conditions of modern risks.

Research method or methodology. The article uses the following methods: monographic, analysis and synthesis, systematization.

Presentation of the main material (research results). A close dialectical relationship between the labor market, personnel security and innovative development of entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector has been determined. The labor market is a producer of innovative entrepreneurship and strong personnel security. Due to the availability of human resources on the labor market, which are involved in the production and distribution of innovative goods and services in the agricultural sector. The main hypothesis in the formed context is that without taking into account the trends occurring in the modern labor market, it is practically impossible to form means of state support for the innovative development of the agricultural sector and ways to ensure personnel security.

Field of application of results. The results of the study can be used in the practical activities of agricultural enterprises to reduce the negative impact of risks on the personnel security system.

Conclusions on the article. The main directions of the formation of personnel security of agrarian enterprises have been determined. It is emphasized that innovative entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector strengthens its positive impact on the labor market, which changes and sets the further trend of the development of the national labor market at the expense of stable personnel security. In such a relationship, there is a synergistic effect of entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector, personnel security and the labor market, which determines and determines the current and prospective vector of the development of the national innovation system.

Keywords: personnel security, management system, agricultural enterprises, risk, labor market.

Formulation of the problem. Currently, an important place in the generation of innovative development of agricultural enterprises in the national economy is occupied by personnel security. Effective personnel security contributes to the formation of a competitive environment in the agricultural sector. Personnel security should significantly strengthen its positive influence on the enterprise management system, due to which changes and sets the further trend of the development of the national agricultural sector due to a strong personnel policy.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A large number of scientific works by foreign and domestic scientists are devoted to the issue of personnel security. These are such researchers as: H. Alexander, J. Bailey, Z. Varnalii, V. Zyanko, G. Kozachenko, E. Ovcharenko, Yu. Pogorelov, V. Chernyak, V. Shevchuk and other scientists made a significant contribution to the development of security theory [1–4; 6–12]. At the same time, the polyparadigmatic approach to the phenomenon analyzed by us indicates

the need for constant rethinking of existing scientific achievements, taking into account the rapidly changing modern conditions of socio-economic and political development of the economic system of agro-enterprises. The activation of scientific research in this direction is a prerequisite and an extremely important factor in the strategically balanced formation of personnel security priorities in the conditions of an innovative economy.

The formulation of the goals of the article is to investigate the peculiarities of the formation of personnel security in the management system of agrarian enterprises in the conditions of modern risks.

Presenting main material. The existing proposals regarding the transparency of the conditions for increasing the personnel security of agricultural enterprises should take place by improving the process of forming a critical mass of personnel capable of generating innovative ideas, the dialectic of ensuring the effective interconnection of the labor market and innovative agricultural enter-

prises, especially in an unstable external environment. The principles of the modern development of personnel security and the logic of its state management in market conditions require revision. The accelerated creation of the latest technologies, the widespread progress of robotics and the active development of nanotechnology at the global level caused the entire agricultural economy to enter a phase of powerful progressive socio-economic transformations focused on innovation. This complex and long-term transformation does not bypass any sector of the economy and, accordingly, has a strong impact on personnel security, changing the rules of operation of the agricultural sector and deepening internal polarization. HR policy is under tension, experiencing continuous changes and bifurcations that also affect agribusiness. We believe that innovations and personnel security of agricultural enterprises are dialectically interconnected. The systemic connections between innovation and personnel security are very strong, multifactorial, complex and unpredictable, and therefore have long been of interest to representatives of various schools of economic theory.

In the scientific world, there are constantly diametrically opposed opinions regarding the positive or negative impact of innovations on personnel security. As an example, the question of determining how much new technologies destroy jobs or stimulate their creation. There are active discussions about the most effective and safe ways of adapting human capital to the new conditions of technology development and, in general, the further formation of a comprehensive strategy for the appropriate interaction of the labor market and innovatively oriented agrarian enterprises.

Taking into account the foresight of the national economy, it is obvious that innovative activities in the agricultural sector can create a fundamentally new level of personnel security and destroy outdated trends in it.

In order to determine how personnel security should be improved, it is necessary to analyze national statistical indicators. In particular, the economically active population, according to the methodological explanations of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, is the male and female population aged 15 years and older, who provided an offer on the labor market during the examined week. Potentially, all individuals who are part of the economically active

population are an intangible asset that is represented on the labor market and represents a source of human resources for agricultural enterprises. According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, in 2018, the economically active population aged 15–70 was 17,939.5 thousand people (or 62.6% of the total population of the respective group). Compared to the previous year, it increased by 85.1 thousand people (or by 0.5%). During the studied period, there was an increase in the employment of the population of the appropriate age by 204.5 thousand people (or by 1.3 %) and, accordingly, a decrease in unemployment by 119.4 thousand people (or by 7 %) [5]. At the same time, in 2018, despite the decrease in unemployment among the economically active population, compared to the previous year, its level is quite high – 8.8%. The corresponding average indicator for the EU–28 countries was lower than in Ukraine by 2.0% and amounted to 6.8%. Evaluating the mentioned trends, it is necessary to determine the positive dynamics of the increase of the economically active population, and the unemployed can be a mobilization reserve that can be involved in the innovative activities of agricultural enterprises through the implementation of an effective regulatory policy of employment of the population and thus increase personnel security. It is difficult to accurately assess the current state of personnel security in the field of innovative agribusiness, taking into account the data presented by the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, because there is a significant delay in the publication of statistical information on agricultural enterprises and their personnel support, which practically makes it impossible to realistically assess the current state or the necessary indicators in the context at least last year.

When forming personnel security, it should be taken into account that it is not labor that is sold, but the ability to work. That is why an important condition for the functioning of any agricultural enterprise in the context of innovative development of the national economy is the quality of an intangible asset – personnel that concentrates human capital, which promotes or, on the contrary, inhibits the development of innovations. The human capital of an agro-enterprise includes a combination of educational-professional and intellectual-creative components, determines the degree of innovative saturation of work, its intellectualization, humanization and creativity. Human capital is a concept

that should be explored as a separate theory, but usually human capital is considered as a structural part of intellectual capital. Most often, human capital is described as a set of knowledge, skills, abilities acquired through education and training and subsequently implemented in practical, including entrepreneurial activities in the agricultural sector. Thanks to the work of scientists, lecturers, teachers, managers, doctors, and social workers, innovations are created and implemented in the agricultural sector, favorable conditions are formed for personnel security, which ensures a high standard of living for the population and increases the competitiveness of the national economy. In addition, it is people who are the main carriers of information and knowledge that are distributed on the labor market and accumulated in agribusiness.

Thus, one of the conditions for effective personnel security, in addition to a sufficient number of employees, is the availability of personnel with the appropriate level of human capital, in the form of skills, education, capable of developing and implementing innovations in the agricultural sector. An important indicator that characterizes the involvement of human capital in innovative processes is the employees involved in the performance of scientific and research works (hereinafter referred to as R&D). The percentage distribution of GDR special-

ists (researchers, technicians and support staff) to the entire population of Ukraine involved in the labor market was insignificant and amounted to 0.54%, including researchers – 0.35% [5]. For comparison, according to Eurostat, the highest similar indicators were in Denmark (3.18% and 2.2%), Finland (3.04% and 2.26%), Great Britain (2.29% and 1.68%) and the Netherlands (2.28% and 1.39%); the lowest – in Romania (0.54% and 0.34%), Cyprus (0.87% and 0.62%), Bulgaria (1.09% and 0.71%) and Poland (1.08% and 0.83%) [5].

Personnel security of the agricultural sector is impossible without scientific personnel. Statistical data indicate a rapid reduction of scientific personnel in Ukraine (a 51.2% decrease in the number of researchers in 2018 compared to the same figure in 2010) (Fig. 1), which testifies to the progression of the harmful inertial scenario of the development of Ukrainian science.

We will identify the most important challenges in the labor market for personnel security of agricultural enterprises.

1. Steady depopulation of the population of Ukraine, which reduces the number of people who can be involved in agricultural enterprises.

2. The progressive high level of population aging, which is a significant burden on the Pension Fund and, accordingly, the working-age population, which is already involved in agricultural enterprises.

Fig. 1. The number of researchers involved in the implementation of the GDR in Ukraine, thousands of people Summarized by the authors according to the data: [5]

3. Too low an indicator of the duration and quality of life (especially among the rural population) compared to European countries, which forces people to work primarily to satisfy the lowest needs, according to A. Maslow's pyramid of needs.

4. A critical decrease in the quality of secondary education, which is the foundation for building up further knowledge necessary for the production of innovations, increasing personnel security in the agricultural sector.

5. The lack of connection between the needs of the real labor market and the market of educational services, which creates a shortage of professions that are necessary for the implementation of agribusiness.

Thus, it is possible to define a close dialectical relationship between the labor market, personnel security and innovative development of entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector. The labor market is a producer of innovative entrepreneurship and strong personnel security. Due to the availability of human resources on the labor market, which are involved in the production and distribution of innovative goods and services in the agricultural sector. The main hypothesis in the formed context is that without taking into account the trends occurring in the modern labor market, it is practically impossible to form means of state support for the innovative development of the agricultural sector and ways to ensure personnel security.

Conclusions

So, the main directions of the formation of personnel security of agricultural enterprises have been determined. It is emphasized that innovative entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector strengthens its positive impact on the labor market, which changes and sets the further trend of the development of the national labor market at the expense of stable personnel security. From another point of view, the labor market, due to the available intangible assets, acts as a supplier of human resources for agribusiness, which is the initiator of strengthening personnel security. In such a relationship, there is a synergistic effect of entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector, personnel security and the labor market, which determines and determines the current and prospective vector of the development of the national innovation system.

Список використаних джерел

1. Бондаренко–Берегович В. В. Управління економічною безпекою підприємств хлібопекарської галузі. Дисертація на здобуття наукового ступеня доктора філософії за спеціальністю 051 – економіка. Вінницький національний аграрний університет. Вінниця, 2021. 298 с.

2. Вдовенко Н.М., Федірець О.В., Зось–Кіор М.В., Гнатенко І.А. Роль енергоринку в менеджменті ресурсозбереження та ресурсоефективності конкурентоспроможних підприємств агропродовольчої сфери. Український журнал прикладної економіки. 2020. Том 5. № 4. С. 222–229.

3. Гнатенко І. А. Формування державних пріоритетів розвитку підприємництва в умовах інноваційної економіки. Дисертація на здобуття наукового ступеня доктора економічних наук за спеціальністю 08.00.03, м. Київ, 2020. 516 с.

4. Дуб Б. С. Розвиток системи економічної безпеки агрохолдингів. – Кваліфікаційна праця на правах рукопису. Дисертація на здобуття наукового ступеня кандидата економічних наук (доктора філософії) зі спеціальності 21.04.02 «Економічна безпека суб'єктів господарської діяльності». Черкаський національний університет імені Богдана Хмельницького, ВНЗ «Університет економіки та права «КРОК». Черкаси, Київ, 2021. 356 с.

5. Державна служба статистики України <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>

6. Живко З. Б. Сучасні методи забезпечення надійності персоналу: навчальний посібник у схемах і таблицях. Львів: ЛьвДУВС, 2019. 128 с.

7. Живко З. Б., Кредісов В. А., Гнатенко І. А., Гальонкін С. С. Інституціонально–матрична кластеризація в системі стратегічного управління інноваційною економікою в умовах зміни споживчих переваг, глобалізації, діджиталізації, формування економічної культури суспільства та сталого розвитку. Інвестиції: практика та досвід. 2021. № 21. С. 37–43.

8. Орлова–Курилова О. В., Ольшанський О. В., Буряк Є. В., Овчаренко Є. І. Державне регулювання розвитком інноваційного підприємництва в умовах зміни споживчих переваг: моделювання глобалізаційних та безпекових компонент. Агросвіт. 2021. № 16. С. 18–25.

9. Mayovets Y., Vdovenko N., Shevchuk H., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I. Simulation modeling of the financial risk of bankruptcy of agricultural enterprises in the context of COVID–19. Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design. 2021. № 36. P. 192–198.

10. Rossokha V., Mykhaylov S., Bolshaia O., Diukariev D., Galtsova O., Trokhymets O., Ilin V., Zos–Kior M.,

Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. Management of simultaneous strategizing of innovative projects of agricultural enterprises responsive to risks, outsourcing and competition. *Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design*. 2021. № 36. P. 199–205.

11. Brockova K., Rossokha V., Chaban V., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. Economic mechanism of optimizing the innovation investment program of the development of agro–industrial production. *Management Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development*. 2021. Vol. 43. No. 1. P. 129–135.

12. Mykhailichenko M., Lozhachevska O., Smagin V., Krasnoshtan O., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I. Competitive strategies of personnel management in business processes of agricultural enterprises focused on digitalization. *Management Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development*. 2021. Vol. 43. No. 3. P. 403–414.

References

1. Bondarenko–Beregovych V. V. (2021). Management of economic security of enterprises in the bakery industry. Dissertation for obtaining the scientific degree of Doctor of Philosophy in specialty 051 – economics. Vinnytsia National Agrarian University. Vinnytsia, 298.

2. Vdovenko N., Fedirets O., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I. (2020). The role of the energy market in the management of resource conservation and resource efficiency of competitive enterprises in the agri–food sector. *Ukrayins'kyi zhurnal prykladnoyi ekonomiky [Ukrainian Journal of Applied Economics]*, 5.4, 222–229.

3. Hnatenko I. A. (2020). Formation of state priorities for the development of entrepreneurship in the conditions of the innovative economy. Dissertation for obtaining the scientific degree of Doctor of Economic Sciences by specialty 08.00.03, Kyiv, 516.

4. Dub B. S. (2021). Development of the system of economic security of agricultural holdings. – Qualification work on manuscript rights. Dissertation for obtaining the scientific degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences (Doctor of Philosophy) on the specialty 21.04.02 «Economic security of subjects of economic activity». Cherkasy National University named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, KROC University of Economics and Law. Cherkasy, Kyiv, 356.

5. State Statistics Service of Ukraine <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>

6. Zhivko Z. B. (2019). Modern methods of ensuring personnel reliability: a study guide in diagrams and tables. Lviv: LvDUVS, 128.

7. Zhyvko Z., Kredisov V., Hnatenko I., Galonkin, S. (2021). Institutional–matrix clustering in the system of strategic management of innovative economy in the conditions of change of consumer preferences, globalization, digitalization, formation of economic culture of society and sustainable development. *Investytsiyi: praktyka ta dosvid [Investments: practice and experience]*, 21, 37–43.

8. Orlova–Kurilova O., Olshanskyi O., Buriak Ie., Ovcharenko Ie. (2021). State regulation of the development of innovative entrepreneurship in the face of changing consumer preferences: modeling of globalization and security components. *Agrosvit [Agroworld]*, 16, 18–25.

9. Mayovets Y., Vdovenko N., Shevchuk H., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I. (2021). Simulation modeling of the financial risk of bankruptcy of agricultural enterprises in the context of COVID–19. *Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design*, 36, 192–198.

10. Rossokha V., Mykhaylov S., Bolshaia O., Diukariev D., Galtsova O., Trokhymets O., Ilin V., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. (2021). Management of simultaneous strategizing of innovative projects of agricultural enterprises responsive to risks, outsourcing and competition. *Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design*, 36, 199–205.

11. Brockova K., Rossokha V., Chaban V., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. (2021). Economic mechanism of optimizing the innovation investment program of the development of agro–industrial production. *Management Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development*, 43.1, 129–135.

12. Mykhailichenko M., Lozhachevska O., Smagin V., Krasnoshtan O., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I. (2021). Competitive strategies of personnel management in business processes of agricultural enterprises focused on digitalization. *Management Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development*, 43.3, 403–414.

Дані про авторів

Зось–Кіор Микола Валерійович,

д. е. н., професор, професор кафедри менеджменту ім. І.А. Маркіної, Полтавський державний аграрний університет, м. Полтава, Україна

Гнатенко Ірина Анатоліївна,

д. е. н., професор, професор кафедри підприємництва та бізнесу, Київський національний університет технологій та дизайну, м. Київ, Україна

Прокопенко Олексій Володимирович,

к. філос. н., доцент, доцент кафедри філософії, культурології та інформаційної діяльності, Східноукраїнський національний університет ім. В. Даля, Україна

Data about the authors

Mykola Zos-Kior,

Dr. Sc. (Economics), Professor, Professor of I. Markina
Department of Management,
Poltava State Agrarian University, Poltava, Ukraine

Iryna Hnatenko,

Dr. Sc. (Economics), Professor, Professor of the De-
partment of Entrepreneurship and Business, Kyiv Na-
tional University of Technologies and Design, Ukraine, Kyiv

Valerii Ilin,

Dr. Sc. (Econ), Professor, Professor of the Depart-
ment of Journalism and Advertising,
State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, Ukraine

Oleksii Prokopenko,

PhD in Philosophy, Associate Professor, Associ-
ate Professor of the Department of Philosophy, Cultur-
al Studies and Information Activities, Eastern Ukrainian
National University named after V. Dalya, Ukraine